

HISTORICAL CONDITIONS FOR THE FORMATION OF THE FOUNDATIONS OF INTEGRATED AND INCLUSIVE MUSIC EDUCATION

Kulmatova Khurshida Abdurahmonovna

University of economics and pedagogy: Lecturer at the
Department of Social and Humanitarian Sciences
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ABSTRACT

This article examines the historical, cultural, and pedagogical conditions that shaped the development of integrated and inclusive music education principles. It explores the evolution of teaching approaches for learners with special educational needs in global music education and their implementation in the educational system of Uzbekistan. The study highlights the synthesis of national musical heritage and modern inclusive education practices in forming effective learning models.

At the beginning of the 20th century, significant qualitative changes occurred in the field of education in our country, including in the system of music education. Today, in some music-focused educational institutions in Uzbekistan, students with special educational needs make up to 7% of the total student population. In addition, students with disabilities are successfully studying in music schools across all regions, as well as in a number of major higher music education institutions.

Nevertheless, the state of music education cannot be considered entirely positive. This raises the question: what hinders the development of inclusive education in creative professions, particularly in the field of music?

1. One reason is the medical approach toward students with health problems. For many years in our country, a system has been established in which children with health limitations are educated in special (correctional) institutions, and this has become the norm. As a result, there are cases when the principles of this system are transferred to inclusive education without careful consideration, which can lead to negative outcomes.

2. While special (correctional) education isolates children and adolescents with limited health opportunities from society, inclusive education allows them to learn alongside their peers, socialize, and gain more natural access to professional activities.

3. A deeper understanding, analysis, and comparison of the goals, approaches, methods, techniques, and psychological-pedagogical conditions of these two types of education is required. This enables correct decisions in each specific case. This issue is particularly relevant to the initial professional education processes in the field of musical arts.

4. Currently, in the field of musical inclusion, there is no established methodological foundation that ensures stable interconnection and consistency in the activities of educational institutions. In other words, the chain — primary (children's music school) – secondary

(music college) – higher (conservatory or university music faculty) — has not yet been fully systematized.

Significant progress has been made in education over the past twenty years. This applies to the entire system, from general education schools to secondary specialized and higher education institutions. The scope of admitting individuals with health limitations to these educational institutions has been steadily expanding.

Thus, over the past 25 years, inclusive education has actively developed in the Tashkent region. More than 200 students with disabilities have been able to study in over 10 music schools. In many cases, these students placed in inclusive education settings have achieved significant success in acquiring musical knowledge and skills, won awards in performance competitions, and, most importantly, managed to gain admission to institutions of the next educational stage.

Analyzing the results of implementing inclusive education for individuals with health limitations in general music-oriented educational institutions allows us to draw the following conclusions:

1. Educating individuals with health limitations is a complex process grounded in axiological, psychological, social, and moral-ethical principles that determine the significance of developing general education.

2. The joint education of individuals with different initial abilities continued until the first third of the 19th century, after which children with health limitations were educated in specialized, closed institutions.

3. In the mid-20th century, Western European countries, the United States, and Japan addressed the issue of reintegrating individuals with health limitations into the general education system.

4. In Uzbekistan, inclusive processes began somewhat later — in the 19th century. Local experience was partly shaped by foreign practices, yet largely relied on national traditions.

5. Inclusive musical education is a distinctive field of pedagogy, and its effective implementation requires the creation of special conditions in educational institutions to meet the diverse needs of students with health limitations.

6. Today, technical colleges and higher education institutions admit students with health limitations; however, many theoretical and practical issues concerning inclusive musical education remain unresolved.

There are several reasons for the slow development of this process. The main issues are characterized by the following factors:

- The state standards for secondary specialized education in the field of “Music” hardly include requirements for the knowledge, skills, and competencies necessary to work in an inclusive education setting;

- A system for training and retraining music teachers to work in inclusive environments has not been established;

- The methodological foundation of inclusive education processes in the field of musical arts has not been developed;

• Although inclusive education is developing in music schools, cooperation with professional educational institutions is insufficient, and the principles of continuity and consistency in the educational process have not been established.

A comparison of the standards enshrined in legislation with practical implementation shows that the conditions created for the education and professional training of students with health limitations in the “Music” specialty are still insufficient. Work in this area is often carried out solely through the initiative of dedicated teachers. Therefore, the development and systematization of the inclusive musical education system today require significant modernization

An effective way to address this problem is to develop a scientifically grounded pedagogical model of effective musical education for individuals with health limitations and implement it in practice. Such a model should ensure positive and predictable outcomes in the educational process.

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